

obtained by growing the fungus in Czapek's pectin broth were treated with different concentrations of the fungicide (0, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1%) and assayed for production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase. The activity of the enzymes cellulase (C₁), cellulase

(C_x), and β-glucosidase also were estimated.

Production of protopectinase, polygalacturonase, polygalacturonate *trans* eliminase, and pectin *trans* eliminase by *R. solani* was markedly inhibited in all concentrations of carbendazim (see table). Highest reduction was in 0.1% concentration.

Activity of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) also was markedly inhibited. Highest inhibition of cellulase (C₁) and cellulase (C_x) activities was in 0.1% concentration.

Increases in carbendazim concentrations increased β-glucosidase activity. The increase was highest in 0.1% concentration. □

Influence of carbendazim concentrations on in vitro production of pectinolytic and cellulolytic enzymes by *R. solani*.

Fungicide concentration (%)	Proto pectinase production ^a	Poly galacturonase production ^b	Poly galacturonate <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^c	Pectin <i>trans</i> eliminase production ^d	Cellulase activity units (C ₁)	Cellulase activity units (C _x) ^e	β-glucosidase ^f activity
0 (control)	++++	48.50	34.4	22.3	3.500	41.10	3.000
0.01	+++	32.60	24.7	17.1	2.350	30.33	3.532
0.05	++	28.50	18.8	13.4	1.797	25.54	4.246
0.1	+	8.10	8.5	6.4	0.812	13.22	4.925

^a Maceration of potato disc, + to ++++ = increase in activity. ^b Percent loss in viscosity of 0.75% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^c Percent loss in viscosity of 1.2% sodium polypectate after 120 min. ^d Percent loss in viscosity of 1% citrus pectin after 120 min. ^e Percent loss in viscosity of 0.5% carboxy methyl cellulose after 120 min. ^f mg of reducing sugars liberated from 1% arbutin/100 ml.

Evaluating fungicides to control rice leaf scald (LSc) in the field

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We tested five fungicides against LSc *Gerlachia oryzae* Has. and Yokogi under field conditions 1987-88.

Rice cultivar Lalat was planted in 4 × 5-m plot at 15 × 20-cm spacing in a randomized block design with three replications. Plants were artificially inoculated during the evening 25 d after transplanting (DT) with a suspen-

sion of 30,000 spores/ml, using a plastic atomizer.

Seed treatment involved soaking seeds in carbendazim + thiram suspension for 12 h before sowing. Fungicides were sprayed at 30, 40, and 50 DT. Disease incidence was measured 55 DT.

Seed treatment with carbendazim + thiram was effective. Among spray treatments, thiophanate-methyl was most effective in reducing disease (see table). Carbendazim and maneb also significantly reduced disease. No phytotoxicity occurred in any treatment. □

Tungro (RTV) incidence in wetbed seedling nursery

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Rice farmers often raise nurseries in areas adjacent to the fields. Unprotected nurseries are suspected to play an important role in the spread of RTV.

We studied RTV incidence on rice seedlings in an unprotected wetbed nursery. Pregerminated TN1 seeds were sown in a 2 × 10-m nursery laid out in the middle of a field planted to TN1 with high RTV incidence.

At 21 d after seeding (DM), green leafhopper (GLH) in the nursery and in the plants surrounding the nursery were sampled by 10 sweeps of an insect net. GLH infectivity was tested by introducing one captured vector into a test tube containing a TN1 seedling for 24-h inoculation. Seedlings were indexed for RTV by ELISA 3 wk later.

At 21 DAS, seedlings in the field nursery were pulled and apportioned to cover four 7.5 × 8-m plots in the insect-proof screenhouse and four 5.5 × 9-m plots in the field. Two to three

Control of rice LSc disease by fungicides. Bhubaneswar, India, 1987-88.

Treatment	Application rate (kg/ha)	Disease incidence ^a (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1987	1988	1987	1988
Carbendazim + thiram (1:1) ^b	0.035 + 0.105	25.00 (28.31)	28.80 (32.45)	2.5	2.4
Carbendazim	0.8	16.80 (24.19)	27.20 (31.43)	2.8	2.5
Thiophanate-methyl	0.8	11.07 (19.43)	19.60 (26.27)	2.9	2.9
Maneb	1.0	23.20 (28.79)	27.90 (31.88)	2.7	2.4
Blitox	1.0	27.40 (31.56)	29.90 (33.14)	2.6	2.3
Control (unsprayed)		41.93 (40.35)	46.10 (42.76)	2.2	1.8
LSD (0.05)		2.4	2.28	0.3	0.3
(0.01)		3.41	3.24	0.4	0.3

^a Figures in parentheses are the transformed angular values. ^b Chemicals used as seed treatment.

seedlings were planted per. hill. No insecticide was applied. All plants were scored for symptoms at 20 and 35 DT. Virus infection was indexed by ELISA from leaves taken from each hill in a sample of 5 × 5 hills. Ten samples were taken in W-pattern from each plot.

More *Nephotettix virescens* than *N. nigropictus* were collected within the nursery, but numbers were similar in the surrounding plants. Fewer infective GLH were found in the nursery (Table 1).

At 20 DT, RTV incidence was lower in plants in the screenhouse than in the field. At 35 DT, only a slight increase in incidence was observed in the screenhouse; in the field, incidence was nearly 100% (Table 2). This also indicates the low increase in number of GLH in the screenhouse, although it is suitable for GLH development.

Even under high disease and vector pressures, the unprotected wetbed seedling nursery had low RTV incidence. This may be due to the loss of

Table 1. GLH and infective vectors collected from a TN1-seeded nursery in the center of a RTV-affected field and from plants surrounding the nursery. IIRRI, 1989.

Collection site	GLH/10 sweeps ^a (no.)		Infective GLH ^b (%)		
	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	<i>Nephotettix nigropictus</i>	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
In the nursery	45	9	0	3	1
Around the nursery	25	22	3	10	0

^a21 DAS. ^bNo infective *N. nigropictus* was obtained. Infectivity of 80 GLH/site was tested using 1 GLH/TN1 seedling for 24-h inoculation in test tube at 21 DAS. RTBV = rice tungro bacilliform virus, RTSV = rice tungro spherical virus. Plants were assayed by ELISA 21 d after inoculation.

Table 2. RTV incidence based on symptoms and infection by RTBV and RTSV of TN1 plants^a at 20 and 35 d after transplanting (DT) in the screenhouse and in the field. IIRRI, 1989.

	RTV incidence (%)							
	20 DT			35 DT				
	Visual score	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV	Visual score	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV
Screenhouse	1	2	3	1	7	7	5	4
Field	27	24	7	14	99	91	4	3

^aFrom a 2- × 10-m nursery at the center of a RTV-infected field. Plants were indexed by ELISA.

vector infectivity after feeding on seedlings in succession and to the low probability of the vector recovering its

infectivity by feeding on diseased seedlings. □

Effect of foliar application of various salts on rice sheath rot (ShR) disease

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We studied the effectiveness of different salts in controlling ShR incidence in rice crop in the greenhouse and in the field.

In the greenhouse experiment, two seeds of susceptible cultivar ADT38 were planted/clay pot, 5 pots/treatment, with five replications. At 90 d after seeding, eight salts at three concentrations were spray applied.

The plants were artificially inoculated with ShR pathogen *Acrocylin-drium oryzae* Sawada 24 h after spraying by inserting a diseased grain into the leaf sheath. ShR incidence was recorded 15 d after inoculation.

Sprays of calcium sulfate and magnesium sulfate up to 0.2% con-

centration reduced ShR incidence (Table 1).

The field experiment Sep-Feb 1989 (when disease incidence was high) was laid out in 4.5- × 2.0-m plots in a complete random block design with four replications. Susceptible cultivar Co 43 was transplanted 11 Sep, 30 d after seeding.

Recommended 150-60-30 kg NPK/ha was applied as urea, super-phosphate, and muriate of potash. P

and K were basal; N was applied in three equal splits at planting, tillering, and panicle initiation.

Nine salts were mixed in water and sprayed at the boot leaf stage and 15 d later (the check was sprayed with plain water). ShR incidence was measured as percentage tillers affected on randomly selected 25 hills/plot.

Manganese sulfate, calcium sulfate, ferrous sulfate, and copper sulfate gave ShR incidence significantly lower than that of the check (Table 2). □

Table 1. Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence in the greenhouse.

Salt	Disease intensity ^a at given concentration		
	0.2%	0.5%	1.0%
Calcium sulfate	1.3	1.5	1.0
Magnesium sulfate	1.3	1.5	2.4
Copper sulfate	5.7	5.6	7.5
Ferrous sulfate	4.0	5.0	2.3
Zinc sulfate	5.0	2.8	1.9
Nickel nitrate	4.7	5.0	1.9
Sodium fluoride	4.0	1.0	1.2
Ammonium molybdate ^b	1.4	2.5	2.0
Untreated check	-	-	6.0

^aStandard evaluation system for rice, 0-9 scale. ^bTested at 10, 50, and 100 ppm.

Table 2. Effect of various salts on rice ShR incidence in the field. Aduthurai, India, Sep-Feb 1989.

Treatment	Concentration	Mean ShR (%)
Zinc sulfate	10 ⁻² M	22.3
Manganese sulfate	10 ⁻² M	14.0
Copper sulfate	10 ⁻² M	19.0
Calcium sulfate	10 ⁻² M	16.7
Ferric chloride	10 ⁻² M	25.6
Magnesium sulfate	10 ⁻² M	22.2
Ferrous sulfate	10 ⁻² M	18.2
Sodium borate	10 ⁻² M	20.1
Ammonium molybdate	10 ⁻³ M	24.3
Untreated check		31.2
LSD (P=0.05)		6.6